

THE ROLE OF CARTOONS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Annotation. This research is devoted to the study of techniques and methods of teaching English, namely the memorization of lexical units and the identification of the most effective way to motivate students to learn English. The work presents a description of the methods and techniques of teaching a foreign language through viewing cartoons, as well as the depth of understanding the importance of learning English by schoolchildren.

Аннотация. Данное исследование посвящено изучению способов и методов преподавания английского языка, а именно запоминанию лексических единиц и выявлению наиболее эффективного способа мотивации студентов к изучению английского языка. В работе представлено описание методов и приемов обучения иностранному языку через просмотр мультфильмов, а также глубина понимания важности изучения английского языка школьниками.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu tadqiqot ingliz tilini o'qitish usullarini o'rganishga, ya'ni leksik birliklarni yodlashga va o'quvchilarni ingliz tilini o'rganishga undaydigan eng samarali usulni aniqlashga bag'ishlangan. Asarda multfilmlarni tomosha qilish orqali chet tilini o'qitish usullari va usullarining tavsifi berilgan, shuningdek,

o'quvchilar tomonidan ingliz tilini o'rganishning ahamiyatini tushunish chuqurligi aniqlangan .

Key words: cartoons, speech, children, methods, language, foreign.

Ключевые слова: мультфильмы, речь, дети, методы, язык, иностранный.

Kalit soʻzlar: multfilmlar, nutq, bolalar, usullar, til, xorijiy.

English becomes the world's first universal language. The language is the mother tongue of 500 million people in 12 countries. But another 600 million speaks English as a second language.

I assume that educational cartoons are the most effective way to memorize English vocabulary and learn English for schoolchildren.

There are several versions of the appearance of the first cartoon.

According to one version, the French, as the founders of this form of art, are considered the birthday of animation on August 30, 1877. It was on this day that the invention of the praxinoscope was patented by the French artist and self-taught inventor Emil Reynaud. A little earlier, on July 20, 1877, Emite Reynaud presented a report to members of the French Academy and demonstrated a praxinoscope - a device assembled from a box of cookies and a mirror drum, and allowing to view phase pictures on a transparent tape that create the illusion of movement of figures. The first cartoon was created in 1892, when the first session of "light pantomimes" took place. at the Emile Reynaud Optical Theatre. Raynaud painted, painted and edited all his "films" himself, applying images to long tapes, each plot consisted of several hundred pictures.

According to another version, in 1906, the choreographer of the Mariinsky Theater, Alexander Shiryaev, created the world's first puppet cartoon, which depicts 12 dancing figures against the background of still scenery. The film was shot on 17.5 mm film. The time to create it took three months. During the creation, Shiryaev

wiped a hole in the floor with his feet, as he constantly walked from the movie camera to the scenery and back.

To make it easier for children to learn English, educational English cartoons were invented. They were created in the UK, they are designed for children who are learning the language. In such cartoons, grammar is explained in a fun and funny way, with the help of animation, new words and expressions are introduced funny characters such as Dasha the traveler, Diego, Sam the fireman, Pocoyo and many others try to teach children the language.

Educational cartoons are simply necessary. In them, all information is presented in an accessible and understandable form for the child, and the animation is appropriate.

It is also good to watch a cartoon because the child immediately remembers the correct pronunciation of the word and repeats it several times.

It is no coincidence that animated films are loved by children of all ages.

Bright, spectacular, imaginative on the one hand, and simple, unobtrusive, accessible on the other, cartoons are close in their developing, educational possibilities to a fairy tale, a game, live human communication. Cartoon characters show the child a variety of ways to interact with the outside world. Through comparing himself with his favorite characters, the child has the opportunity to perceive himself positively, cope with his fears and difficulties, and treat others with respect. The events taking place in the cartoon make it possible to raise the child's awareness, develop his thinking and imagination, and form his worldview. Thus, a cartoon is an effective means of raising a child, the main thing is to find a golden mean. Watching the "right" cartoons has a number of positive aspects:

the child has the opportunity to relax and distract himself, get psychological relief;

the child learns to perceive the plot and think logically;

cognitive and educational influence (explain natural phenomena, develop speech,

broaden horizons, etc.);

changing the picture on the screen with sound stimulates visual and auditory attention, contributing to their development;

joint viewing of cartoons with parents helps -to find new interesting topics for discussion that develops the child's speech.

The main methods of learning English. The most key moment in learning English is the way of presenting information to the student, otherwise called the teaching method. A good way to assimilate and understand information is to perceive it in a different form.

Such as watching cartoons in a foreign language, listening, reading interesting (fairy tales, short stories), computer games. They make students active participants in the educational process, increase their motivation and interest in studying the subject.

Watching cartoons. Watching cartoons in English will be useful for children with different types of memory. In addition, it should be remembered that cartoons, first of all, are aimed at a children's audience, as a result, when voicing cartoons in English, the rules of pronunciation of the classical variant of the English language are observed. Watching cartoons will be useful at the initial stages of language learning, since cartoons in English do not contain slang, complex grammatical turns, and the pace of speech in cartoons is measured and will not cause difficulties in understanding, in combination with clear diction.

In addition, these fairy tales will help solve one of the main problems when learning a foreign language - perception of English speech by ear. Also, children easily master intonation and pronunciation and undoubtedly replenish their vocabulary and remember it better. Cartoon songs are also easily remembered by children, as the melodies and lyrics are simple.

Listening. Listening at the initial stage of training is one of the most relevant topics,

since speech communication is impossible without listening. Listening (understanding of auditory speech) forms the basis of communication, and mastering communication begins with it. Listening can be a separate type of communicative activity with its own motive, reflecting the needs of a person or the nature of his activities. For example, when watching a cartoon movie, TV show, using the Internet, listening to a radio show, etc. Sufficient mastery of listening as a type of speech activity not only allows, but also stimulates independent viewing of films and TV shows in a foreign language. The main mental processes that are involved in listening are the following: memory, imagination, perception and thinking. Thus, by activating these features of the human psyche, we simultaneously develop them, which is a fundamental factor in the comprehensive development of personality.

Listening is the basis of communication, and the mastery of oral speech begins with it communication. Possession of such a type of speech activity as listening allows a person to understand what is being reported to him and respond adequately to what is said, helps to correctly state his answer to the opponent, which is the basis of dialogic speech. In this case, listening teaches the culture of speech: listen carefully to the interlocutor and always listen to the end, which is important not only when talking in a foreign language, but also in your native language.

Games in cartoons. Games should not and cannot be the main way to learn a language, but they can be used at any stage of learning. They will work especially effectively where it is necessary to attract and interest the child. Such games help in expanding the vocabulary of the English language. However, it is important to pay attention to the translation of terms, find their other meanings in the dictionary and apply them in English language lessons.

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